

This document contains the thematic model we synthesized based on interview materials in our study.

The thematic model is divided into two parts, namely **Practices** and **Challenges**, for testing autonomous driving systems in the industry, with a particular focus on scenario-based approach. The thematic model is synthesized from right to left, meaning we start by analysing the code, then derive lower level themes, and gradually converge to the top (1st) level theme.

* To avoid repeatedly revisiting the original interviews in subsequent analysis, we keep the **Code** short but self-contained, meaning we incorporate necessary information, context, and some examples in the code to a minimum extent to index relevant segments we identified from the interview materials.

1st-level Theme	2nd-level Theme	3rd-level Theme	4th-level Theme	5th-level Theme	Code	Participant	
	Type of testing	Conventional testing			Conventional testing are also used, such as unit test, interface compliance test, application test, integration test, regression test, and delivery test.	P9-10	
		Simulation testing	SIL testing			Daily work responsibilities mainly lie in SIL testing: monitor the test results from the test pipeline where it executes test scenarios in simulation and analyse the failures as well as to resolve them with the developers. Then, regression testing is performed after introducing any changes.	P9-10
			HIL testing			HIL testing is performed for an AD platooning project for testing communication between vehicles.	P9-10
			Component-specific			For simulation testing of post-perception modules of AV, no sensor simulation or synthetic sensor data is needed. We could define desired inputs from perception in the simulation interface and use that for testing the accuracy, completeness, etc. of post-perception modules.	P9-10
						Tools and methods are different for testing different components of the system, we try to do virtual testing as much as possible.	P5
		Scenario-based testing	Scenario simulation			Scenario-based testing is essential when you use simulation, as you don't randomly simulate the environment and driving situations, but with different scenarios (with specific objects, interactions, weather, etc.) according to some predefined use cases.	P2
			Critical scenarios			Use critical scenarios as one piece in the big puzzle for testing ADS.	P8
			Modules and full AV stack			Scenario-based testing approach is used for perception module, post-perception modules, and the full AV stack.	P9-10
			AEB			For AEB system, true full breaks (expected behaviors) are also tested in NCAP testing program besides hazardous events.	P8
		Test principle	Waterfall			Scenario-based testing is performed in pre-defined times based on the project milestones. The project uses waterfall and each test campaign can run for couple of weeks in this EU project for AD.	P1
	Agile				In the automotive industry, the process is more agile and testing is conducted and improved iteratively, which means code change will trigger the entire pipeline, including simulation testing, HIL testing, and finally, it will reach to real-world testing with the system deployed on a real vehicle.	P1	
	Iterative V-model				Testing from a single component to a complete vehicle.	P5	
					Iterative V-model that iterates the V-model development and testing.	P5	
	Test scenario selection	Multi-tiered approach	Component-specific			Test scenarios are selected based on which component to test and what has been changed for it.	P11
			Necessity for testing			A set of scenarios are selected and are always mandatory to test and pass for every code change, including simple and common scenarios.	P11
			Safety and functionality			The test scenarios are continuously expanding from safety perspective and functionality perspective.	P11
		Implementation-specific			Test approaches and scenarios for perception and post-perception modules are different due to their different implementation. Perception uses open-loop testing, and post-perception and full AV stack use closed-loop testing.	P9-10	
		ODD specification			Inclusion and exclusion of test scenarios should be based on ODD specification.	P6-7	
					Excluding test scenarios based on probability of occurrence in ODD.	P6-7	
		Standards and regulations			For ADAS, selecting test scenarios is not a problem because a specific set of test scenarios is defined, for example, by EuroNCAP.	P2	
		Responsibilities	Testers and function owners			The testers and function owners select, execute, and evaluate the test scenarios that are relevant for the AD function.	P11
			Developers			Initiatives of having other roles (e.g., developers) except testers to create test scenarios for system under test as they know the system better.	P11
			Functional teams			Responsibility division on autonomous driving stack is also applicable for testing, so each team/layer is responsible for testing their own deliverables, but also involved in overall system testing.	P4
			Test teams and			There are specific teams (of test engineers) look into the systems and testing strategies to define which test to perform (HIL, vehicle test, integration test, etc.), and test scenarios, including the edge cases (critical scenarios).	P1

Practices	Test scenario identification		product owner		The product owner is responsible, in collaboration with the test teams, to control and confirm that the tests are correctly developed and verified according to the company strategies.	P1	
		Level of automation	Manual		Defining, creating, and executing test scenarios are still very manual, and happen on a regular basis, for example, when changing ODD or after milestone reviews, and is part of the integration and release testing.	P4	
		Knowledge-based				We use domain experts to derive all test scenarios.	P11
						Test scenarios are predefined based on knowledge-based approaches, including extracting or deriving from the standards, experiences, and peer-review results, and are collected in a scenario library.	P9-10
						Top-down approach in identifying possible scenarios using the experts, because we have to think and test those scenarios before rather than testing them on public roads.	P3
						Test scenario identification is expert-based and involves several companies and academies in multiple workshops.	P1
						We are dabbling into the data-driven approach for scenario identification.	P11
		Data-driven	Re-simulation			One way of doing data-driven approach is to re-simulate scenarios collected and test the system based on that.	P11
			Extraction			Extract and reproduce the scenarios from collected data in the test environment.	P5
			AEB			For AEB system, we test hazardous events, e.g., a false full break, and analyse how we can minimize that.	P8
		Search-based	Extrapolation			Collect substantial driving data takes time, so we collect some data and extrapolate from the data (known scenarios) to find unknown scenarios and cover the entire ODD (find the boundaries).	P5
		Combined				Every approach has its limitations, so research on these approaches and combining them to address the current gaps are needed.	P2
						There are a lot of initiatives to complement the expert approach, but not to replace. For example, we can complement the expert approach with simulation testing, closed-track testing, and other data sources available.	P3
						One limitation is that knowledge-based approach alone is not enough and we have to complement it with other approaches.	P3
	Limitations	Knowledge-based approaches	Coverage		Expert approach gives a good foundation for testing and allows progressing rapidly in the beginning, but there is a ceiling on the coverage.	P11	
			Interpretation		The challenge is that we need to learn from these data and identify relevant test scenarios from it.	P3	
		Data-driven approaches	Visualization		A problem with data-driven approach is to have a good visualization system (such as simulation) to capture enough information from data and represent the scenario as in the real-world context.	P11	
			Relevance		A critical accident for a human driver who speeding up to 200km/h and collide is irrelevant because AV should maintain the speed under the limit.	P2	
	Maturity of testing	Metrics			Different metrics are used to demonstrate the maturity of the system and its testing, e.g., more scenarios are passed in test, perception of objects with higher accuracy, and smooth reactions to road events within a short time.	P9-10	
			Mileage-based		Mileage-based metric is used to indicate safety or test maturity of AV.	P5	
		Standards satisfaction			We need to argue safety based on resources and results we have, but also need to be aware of the gaps between the results and public standards as well as the common acceptance criteria in the industry.	P9-10	
		Use all resources			Put all resources, e.g., experts, fleet test data, together to demonstrate and improve safety (e.g., less collisions).	P8	
		Safety	Safe enough	Redundancy		Being safe does not mean 100% complete (all possible scenarios are tested and handled), and there could be scenarios that are not tested but still maintain the safety (or safe enough) of ADS using for example redundancy.	P8
	Defensive driving for unknowns				Slow down or pullover the vehicle if scenarios can not be handled emerge, as an example of being safe.	P8	
	Residual risks				Even with the residual risks and potential hazards might occur, AVs are still said to improve the overall safety of road traffic for avoiding for example, many deaths from alcohol, speeding, and distraction during driving.	P2	
	Test analysis and demonstration	Completeness	Use all resources		Use available standards (e.g., SOTIF) and test results (e.g., hazardous analysis, acceptance criteria) to demonstrate the test completeness.	P8	

		Limitations of metrics	Mileage-based		Mileage-based metric is not comprehensive and needs to be complemented with other metrics. Doing a simple and common scenario, e.g., a car-following scenario on the highway, for millions of miles does not prove the overall safety of the system.	P9-10	
					Mileage-based metric is subject to trust in AV and skills of safety drivers and can be faulted.	P5	
			Coverage-based		It is not realistic to have 100% coverage for all possible scenarios in testing, instead we need to demonstrate a sufficient coverage of scenarios to support the safety argument based on the potential risk assessment.	P9-10	
Standards	General-purpose		SOTIF				
			openX ASAM		Other standards used for testing include for example, SOTIF, new openX ASAM standard, ISO-34501-34505.	P9-10	
			ISO-34501-34505				
			ISO TS 5083		ISO/PAS-21448, and development of new standards, e.g., ISO TS 5083 for testing safety and cybersecurity for AD systems.	P1	
	Function-specific	UN No.157	LKS	Legal requirements (UN regulation No. 157) for testing AD function (Lane-Keeping System).	P8		
					Current standards are immature and need to evolve with the support of experts, academia, and thus; the standards are just a baseline.	P9-10	
Limitations					SOTIF gives you a reference how you think of the problem, but does not solve the problem of testing AV since we don't know the 'unknowns'.	P2	
		Only serve as a baseline			Another problem comes with SOTIF is that you never know a scenario is safe or not until you test it. Thus, it's not just unknown hazardous scenarios that we should focus, but all relevant scenarios to assure they are safe.	P2	
					The minimum for safety of AV is to follow all relevant standards, tick off homologation and approaches to assure the vehicle is safe.	P5	
					Use simulation is efficient and cheap compared to the on-road testing.	P6-7	
					Collecting data and testing ADS on public roads is expensive. If simulation testing can be improved and used for demonstrating the safety of ADS to minimize/shift the on-road driving, that would change the current situation a lot.	P1	
					Partnership with technical (AD stack) suppliers, data and tool suppliers, simulation suppliers, and do benchmarking of them, etc.	P5	
Tools and platforms	Simulation	Efficiency and low-cost					
	Collaboration	Data					
		AD software					
		Tools					
Simulation							
General initiatives	Collaboration				More research and collaboration are needed between different entities.	P5	
			Data ecosystem		The industry doesn't really know and academia may help with all the available data on how to select right data to support, for example, the development of their systems or shortening the testing time.	P1	
					Academic can support due to its neutral position in fostering collaboration and ecosystem initiatives.	P9-10	
					A continuous approach for testing to go along with the development.	P1	
				Continuously learn the field of testing ADS.	P8		
		Tools and methods		Continuously evolve the technologies, methods, tools, and practices as well as filling in the current gaps.	P5, P8		
	Continuously learn and improve		Collection and learning		Continuously collect and learn from data as well as monitoring the function behavior.	P8	
			Data	Scenario distribution	Based on the data, we find some rare-occurring scenarios, and the probability of scenarios in real traffic.	P5	
				Scenario catalogue	Create and expand the scenario catalogue based on the collected data.	P5	
				Resource allocation	Allocate test resource based on probability of scenarios in real traffic.	P6-7	
		Regression testing	Feedback loop for changes	Use regression testing as the system is continuously developed. We can't rethink everything for a single change and we need to have a feedback loop (what we have changed and how does it affect the system as well as testing).	P3		

		Combine different approaches	Take all resources and approaches		Testing of ADS is unsolved yet and different sources and approaches are needed, so we have to look at different approaches, data, and tools.	P4
					We can never say the scenarios we find and test are complete, but we take each solution as a basis and one piece of the entire solution.	P8
Challenges	Discrepancies	Concepts	Safety		Discrete safety definitions and concepts exist and used by different companies, but no standards and guidelines for them.	P5
		Approaches	Data processing		Research is needed to get public data and statistics on for example, accident scenarios and hazards, every OEM sits on their own and an internationally accepted one is needed.	P12-13
			Testing process		An open challenge is do things collectively (industry, researchers, authorities) in a more aligned/standard approach, as right now every OEM is using their own approach to collect data, to do the testing, etc., and is a waste of resources. OEMs can learn from each other.	P12-13
			Standards and regulations	Regulation	Immature	AD regulation is immature but is improving, for example, remote operation capability.
		Lacking of			The biggest challenge for testing AV is not on the technical side, but rather the process and regulation side. What is the safety standard and who owns the liability, and how should we test the systems?	P3
		Demonstration/Argumentation of safety		Safety	How to prove the safety of the system and vehicle?	P6-7
				It's not perfect even for AEB, and we can only argue (the safety) from what we know, for example, zero-death.	P8	
	Euro NCAP			We need to prove the safety for certifying AV. Euro NCAP is insufficient for AD, but more for performance evaluation for Active Safety systems.	P8	
	Technology immature			Technology is immature for high-level, for example, L4 AD systems.	P8	
	Testing process and methods	Complexities	Uncertainties	The current process becomes the bottleneck or major challenge because of the complexities and uncertainties (scenarios, environment, system behaviors) for the ADS. It is a rather new topic involves many areas.	P3	
			System-of-systems	Testing of ADS is a big challenge as different sensors, deep learning systems are used for perception, decision, and control in ADS.	P4	
		Cost- and time-consuming	On-road testing	Testing on public roads for billions of kms is not realistic, and for deep learning and autonomous driving, specific test scenarios are more important than driving mileage, and those scenarios that we try to create and use for testing (e.g., the safety) are considered critical scenarios.	P4	
		Delays of test	Deep learning	The challenge comes with deep learning is that we gradually understand more of the testing after we build the system, which means the testing is delayed or falling behind until we know how to test them.	P4	
		Insufficiencies	Collection and aggregation		How to deal with sensor fusion with data in different formats and volumes?	P6-7
					To test each functionality, we need to figure out the best criteria to evaluate and metrics to measure the quality or performance of it. For perception, the biggest challenge for testing is to define a representative test data set that includes all possible user cases (scenarios).	P4
				Collecting data from different sources, e.g., test vehicles, accident databases, and other data from the suppliers as well.	P5	
				A lot of challenges appear with data, e.g., whether the data is enough, how to identify and extract scenarios with naturalistic driving data, etc.	P2	
	Interpretation, extraction, and extrapolation			From collected data, we need to understand for example, the possible scenarios, traffic densities, driver behaviors, etc.	P5	
				Big companies like Waymo collect substantive data (both in real-world and in simulation) in mileage, but how relevant these mileage is, and how many scenarios it actually covers, are still unknown to us.	P2	
				We need to extrapolate unknown scenarios from known scenarios.	P5	
	Maintainance			Another challenge is the complexity of maintaining the data when sensor suite evolves, for example, new sensor dependencies are introduced.	P11	
	Generalizability			Research is needed to get public data and statistics on for example, accident scenarios and hazards, every OEM sits on their own and a internationally accepted one is needed.	P12-13	
			Statistics of driving data in a country or region may not be scaled to a more international environment, thus statistics (e.g., collision rates, occurrence rates) that are more internationally accepted is strongly demanded.	P12-13		
Ecosystem			Data-driven approach is the priority and an ecosystem and collaboration are needed for that.	P9-10		

				Ecosystem	Data collection for developing and testing AD systems, and tool-chain to support the use of data, testing, etc. are two challenges.	P9-10	
				ML training	How to include identified critical scenarios in the training data set for ML-based systems?	P6-7	
					How to train sophisticated ML models to learn human knowledge and risk assessment?	P6-7	
		Assessment		Completeness	For ADS, no one probably has a complete set of test scenarios, you need to make the scenario catalog bigger and create pass-fail criteria for them.	P2	
						The problem with scenario-based testing is how many scenarios do we need, how many scenarios do we know, and how complete are they.	P2
						For full ADS you must test and verify that you cover all possible scenarios, so that you have the confidence or backup (driver to take over).	P3
						One single approach can not prove the completeness of testing.	P8
					Probability of occurrence	An open challenge is the statistics of occurrence of scenarios.	P12-13
					System performance	With machine-learning systems, we have a more open input space and every input leads to a probabilistic instead of a specific output, and it's hard to set the boundary or threshold where the decision should divert.	P3
						Noises could lead the machine learning model make a different decision for the same input, thus are non-deterministic.	P3
					Transferrability of test results	Quality or fidelity of simulation is another big challenge for scenario-based testing that many people do not believe in the simulation as it cannot represent the reality.	P4
						How to move from simulation to the real world?	P6-7